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Principal's Managerial Competencies As Predictors Of Teacher Productivity In Public Senior Secondary Schools In Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

This study examined principal's managerial competencies as predictors of teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Two objectives, two research questions and two corresponding null hypotheses guided the study. The study was anchored on transformational leadership theory. The study adopted a correlational research design with a population of 276 principals in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. A sample size for the study was 276 principals drawn using the census sampling technique. The instruments for data collection were two researcher's developed questionnaire titled: "Principal's Managerial Competencies Questionnaire (PMCQ) and Teacher Productivity Questionnaire (TPQ)". The instruments were validated by the researcher's supervisors and three experts in the field of Measurement and Evaluation of the Department of Educational Psychology, Guidance and Counselling of the University of Port Harcourt. The reliability coefficients of the instruments were determined using Cronbach Alpha Statistics. The reliability coefficients obtained for principal's Managerial Competencies Questionnaire was given at 0.73 while that Teacher Productivity Questionnaire was given at 0.75 respectively. Simple regression was used to answer research questions 1-2 while t-test associated with simple regression was used to test hypotheses 1-2 at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that, to a low extent, principal's managerial competencies such as problem-solving skill, social intelligence, predicts teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State and that there are significant joint prediction of principal's managerial competencies on teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. It was concluded that effective managerial competencies such as problem-solving skill and social intelligence play a pivotal role in enhancing teacher motivation, instructional delivery, and overall productivity. Based on the findings, the study recommended amongst others that government should organize regular training on analytical and critical thinking skills for principals to enhance effective resolution of academic and administrative issues. Regular training should be provided to principals in emotional intelligence to better understand and respond to the emotional and social needs of teachers.

Keywords: Principal's Managerial Competencies, Teacher Productivity, Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

INTRODUCTION

Education is a process of acquiring knowledge, skills, values, beliefs and habits that shape an individual's understanding of the world and their role within it. It is both a personal and societal journey that begins at birth and continues throughout life, encompassing formal settings like schools and universities as well as informal learning through experiences and interactions. The concept of education goes beyond academic instruction. It aims to develop critical thinking, creativity, ethical reasoning, emotional intelligence, and a sense of responsibility. Education serves as a foundational tool for individual empowerment, enabling people to realise their potential, improve their quality of life, and contribute meaningfully to their communities. The values of education include fostering respect for diversity, promoting social justice, encouraging lifelong learning, and nurturing a commitment to the common good. Education instils virtues such as honesty, discipline, cooperation, empathy, and resilience. Ultimately, education is essential not only for personal growth but also for the progress and sustainability of societies, as it equips citizens with the awareness and competencies needed to address global challenges and participate in democratic life. It is therefore, important to note that, secondary school is one aspect of education.

Secondary school administration refers to the process of planning, organising, directing, and controlling the resources and activities of secondary schools to achieve educational objectives. It involves the management of staff, students, curriculum, facilities, and finances, and is primarily carried out by principals. It follows that, school administration is essentially a process through which the fundamental objectives of the educational process may be more fully and efficiently realised. School administration is therefore concerned with the utilization of resources and the harmonization of relationships and interactions in a suitable environment in order to foster the attainment of the goals of teaching and learning. School administration involves prudent management of resources and high degree of accountability on the part of organizational members. It broadly means running of educational institutions, which involves guidance, leadership, and controlling of the efforts of individuals in the achievement of the goals of the institution. All the people working in an educational institutions will have to contribute towards the accomplishment of these goals. It calls for proper managerial competencies.

Managerial competencies refer to a combination of skills, knowledge, and abilities that enable managers to effectively perform their roles and responsibilities. In the context of secondary school administration, managerial competencies are essential for school leaders, such as principals, to efficiently manage school operations, ensure student success, and maintain a positive school environment. These competencies are crucial not only for administrative functions but also for fostering an environment conducive for learning, teacher development, and community involvement. Managerial competencies in human resource management are critical for retaining high-quality teachers. Effective principals know how to evaluate, support, and develop their staff. A report by the Learning Policy Institute (2023) opines that school leadership directly impacts teacher satisfaction and retention. Principals who offer professional development opportunities, maintain a positive work environment, and resolve conflicts effectively create a more stable and effective teaching staff. A school leader's ability to handle these responsibilities directly impacts the school's performance, the wellbeing of staff and students, and the overall success of the educational institution. The importance of the teacher as the curriculum implementer cannot be overemphasized. A study by Darling-Hammond (2017) notes that, teachers with higher levels of education and ongoing professional development are more likely to employ effective teaching strategies, which can lead to improved student outcomes.

Invariably, the nexus between principal's managerial competencies and teacher productivity is an area of significant interest, as effective management is often associated with enhanced performance in educational settings. Managerial competencies refer to the skills, knowledge, and abilities that school leaders such as principals possess to effectively manage school operations, support staff development, and create an environment conducive to student learning. Research by Hoy and Miskel (2013) identify problem solving skill and social intelligence as vital components of principals' managerial competencies. Problem-solving skill is the ability to identify challenges, analyse situations, develop possible solutions, and implement effective strategies to resolve issues. It involves critical thinking, decision-making,

creativity, and emotional intelligence. In educational settings, this skill is essential for leaders like principals who must navigate complex and dynamic school environments. The principals' problem-solving ability significantly influences teacher productivity in secondary schools. Effective principals who demonstrate strong problem-solving skills create supportive environments where challenges are addressed promptly and collaboratively. Duyar (2023) notes that, principals who resolve conflicts and resource issues efficiently contribute to a more positive school climate, motivating teachers.

Social intelligence refers to the ability to understand, navigate, and manage interpersonal relationships and social environments effectively. Goleman (2016) states that, social intelligence encompasses skills such as empathy, social awareness, influence and relationship management. It involves both cognitive and emotional capabilities used in social contexts, allowing individuals to interpret others' behaviours, respond appropriately, and build meaningful connections. In secondary schools, principals with high social intelligence can better school climate, understand student needs, collaborate with colleagues, and communicate effectively with parents and school community. This contributes to a more supportive learning environment and fosters academic and emotional development among students. Invariably, social intelligence plays a vital role in enhancing teacher productivity in secondary schools. It influences classroom interactions, teacher wellbeing, and collaborative practices, all of which are essential for effective teaching and learning. Investing in professional development that fosters social intelligence can lead to more productive and resilient teachers.

The study was anchored on transformational leadership theory by Bernard M. Bass (1985). Transformational leadership theory by Bernard M. Bass (1985) posits that effective leaders inspire, motivate, and challenge followers to achieve exceptional outcomes by focusing on higher-order needs. This theory emphasizes four key components: idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration. Transformational leaders create a vision of the future, challenge conventional norms, encourage innovation, and provide personalized support to followers. This leadership style focuses not only on achieving organizational goals but also on the personal and professional development of employees.

In the context of principals in secondary schools, a transformational principal is one who encourages teacher innovation, builds a positive school culture, and offers professional development opportunities to teachers. Such principals can have a profound effect on teacher motivation, which, in turn, influences teacher productivity. Transformational leadership links managerial competencies to the enhanced productivity of teachers because it stresses the importance of motivation, empowerment, and personal growth in achieving high performance.

Relevance to the Study: This theory is highly relevant to the study of principals' managerial competencies as predictors of teacher productivity because it demonstrates how effective leadership can positively influence teachers' commitment, morale, and performance. Principals who are transformational leaders can create a work environment where teachers are motivated to improve their productivity and achieve educational goals. Through the lens of this theory, the study can examine how a principal's ability to inspire and support teachers impacts their productivity in public secondary schools. Transformational Leadership Theory emphasizes the motivational and inspirational role of the principal in improving teacher performance, while human capital theory focuses on the direct link between investments in teacher development and productivity. Together, these theories offer a comprehensive framework for studying the influence of principal leadership on teacher productivity in public secondary schools.

Statement of the Problem

Education remains a critical pillar for national development, and its effectiveness largely hinges on the productivity of teachers who serve as the direct facilitators of learning. In Nigeria, and particularly in Rivers State, concerns over declining educational outcomes, teachers' motivation, and overall school effectiveness have prompted increased scrutiny into the administrative capabilities of school leaders especially principals. Among the numerous factors that influence teacher productivity, the managerial competencies of school principals have emerged as potentially significant but often relegated to the background.

It has been observed by the researcher that principals serve as the linchpin in the administration of secondary schools. They are expected to perform a wide range of managerial functions including planning, decision-making, staff supervision, communication, conflict resolution, and instructional leadership. However, empirical evidence suggest that, many public senior secondary schools in Rivers State face challenges such as teacher absenteeism, low morale, poor student performance, and ineffective classroom practices. These issues raise critical questions about the capacity of school principals to manage human and material resources effectively in order to stimulate optimal teacher productivity. The problem, therefore, is the apparent disconnect between the managerial roles expected of school principals and the observed level of teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools. If principals lack the necessary managerial competencies or fail to apply them effectively, it could lead to poor teacher performance, which in turn undermines educational quality. This study hopes to address this gap by examining the extent to which principal's managerial competencies predict teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The study examined principal's managerial competencies as predictors of teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Specifically, the objectives were to:

1. examine the extent to which principal's problem solving skill predicts teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. identify the extent to which principal's social intelligence predicts teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. To what extent does principal's problem solving skill predict teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
2. To what extent does principal's social intelligence predict teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H0₁: There is no significant prediction of principal's problem-solving skill on teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

H0₂: There is no significant prediction of principal's social intelligence on teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

The research design of the study was correlation survey design. The population of the study comprised all the 276 principals and 6842 teachers in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State (Rivers State Ministry of Education, 2025). They were selected using the census and proportionate technique. The study used two sets of questionnaire for data collection. The first instrument was titled "Principal's Managerial Competencies Questionnaire (PMCQ) while the second was titled: "Teacher Productivity Questionnaire" (TPQ)" The structured questionnaire were divided into two (2) sections. Section A elicited responses on personal data, while Section B consisted of 10 items structured in line with the 2 research questions of this study. The instruments were modified after 4 points Likert scale type of Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE) scale of responses. There are five items per instrument. The instruments for this study were validated for face and content validity using the supervisors and three (3) experts in the Department of Educational Measurement and Evaluation from the Faculty of Education, University of Port Harcourt. This enabled the researcher to obtain a critical evaluation of the instrument in terms of appropriateness and adequacy. The suggestions from these experts were used to improve the content of the instrument before administration. The reliability of the instruments was determined using Cronbach Alpha. The instruments were retrieved and coded. Each cluster of the questionnaire was analysed to ascertain its reliability index. The reliability

coefficients obtained for Principal’s Managerial Competencies Questionnaire was 0.73 while that of Teacher Productivity Questionnaire was 0.75 respectively. The researcher with the help of three (3) trained research assistants visited the sampled public senior secondary schools in Rivers State to administer the instruments. A total of 276 copies of the questionnaire were administered. After retrieval, the analysis were conducted. Simple regression was used to answer research questions 1-2. t-test associated with simple regression was used to test hypotheses 1-2 at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *To what extent does principal’s problem solving skill predict teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 1: Simple Regression on the Extent principal’s problem solving skill predict teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.168 ^a	.028	.024	.76141

a. Predictors: (Constant), problem-solving skill

Table 1 showed the results of a linear regression carried out to investigate the extent principal’s problem solving skill predicts teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The correlation coefficient (R = 0.16), which showed to a very low extent the principal’s problem solving skill predicts teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The coefficient of determination (R-squared) associated with the linear regression (R) of 0.16 was 0.028. This coefficient of determination (R-squared) indicates that, the principal’s problem solving skill accounted for 2.8% of teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. This is an indication that other factors that affect principal’s problem solving skill predicts teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State accounted for 97.2%. Therefore, to a very low extent, principal’s problem solving skill predicts teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The percentage scale of 97.2% was generated by subtracting 100 from 2.8%.

Research Question 2: *To what extent does principal’s social intelligence predict teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 2: Simple Regression on the Extent principal’s social intelligence predict teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.253 ^a	.064	.060	.74728

a. Predictors: (Constant), social intelligence

Table 2 showed the results of a linear regression carried out to investigate the extent principal’s social intelligence predicts teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The correlation coefficient (R = 0.25), which showed to a very low extent principal’s social intelligence predicts teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The coefficient of determination (R-squared) associated with the linear regression (R) of 0.25 was 0.064. This coefficient of determination (R-squared) indicates that, principal’s social intelligence accounted for 6.4% of teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. This is an indication that other factors affect principal’s social intelligence predicts teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State accounted for 93.6%. Therefore, to a very low extent, principal’s social intelligence predicts

teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The percentage scale of 93.6% was generated by subtracting 100 from 6.4%.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant prediction of principal’s problem-solving skill on teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 3: t-test Associated with Simple Regression analysis on the Prediction of principal’s problem-solving skill on teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Model		Coefficients ^a		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		Unstandardized Coefficients	Std. Error			
	B			Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.455	.169		14.502	.000
	Problem solving skill	.163	.059	.168	2.772	.006

a. Dependent Variable: Teacher Productivity

Table 3 showed the results of regression carried out to investigate whether there was significant prediction of principal’s problem-solving skill on teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The correlation coefficient ($R = 0.16$), but principal’s problem solving skill significantly to the model with $Beta = 0.16$ and the significant value of 0.00 was less than 0.05 , which shows that to a very low extent significant prediction of principal’s problem-solving skill on teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.02$), indicated that 2% of the variance in teacher productivity was explained by principal’s problem solving skill and 98% was not explained. Principal’s problem solving skill contributed significantly to teacher productivity with $F(1, 266) = 7.68$, $p = 0.00$. Therefore, intercept was found in the row labelled (Constant) and slope in the row for the predictor (Problem-Solving Skill). The results of the regression analysis also showed low positive significant prediction of the principal’s problem solving skill on teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, with (slope = 2.45, t-calculated = 14.50, t-tabulated = ± 1.96 , $p < 0.05$). Hence, the researcher rejected the null hypothesis and opted for the alternate hypothesis

that there is a significant prediction of principal’s problem-solving skill on teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant prediction of principal’s social intelligence on teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4: t-test Associated with Simple Regression analysis on the Prediction of principal’s social intelligence on teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Model		Coefficients ^a		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		Unstandardized Coefficients	Std. Error			
	B			Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.140	.186		11.527	.000
	Social Intelligence	.266	.062	.253	4.258	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Teacher Productivity

Table 4 showed the results of regression carried out to investigate whether there was significant prediction of principal's social intelligence on teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The correlation coefficient ($R = 0.25$), but principal's social intelligence significantly to the model with Beta = 0.25 and the significant value of 0.00 was less than 0.06, which shows that to a very low extent significant prediction of principal's social intelligence on teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.06$), indicated that 6% of the variance in teacher productivity was explained by principal's social intelligence and 94% was not explained. Principal's social intelligence contributed significantly to teacher productivity with $F(1, 266) = 18.13$, $p = 0.00$. Therefore, intercept was found in the row labelled (Constant) and slope in the row for the predictor (Social Intelligence). The results of the regression analysis also showed low positive significant prediction of principal's social intelligence on teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, with (slope = 2.14, t-calculated = 11.52, t-tabulated = ± 1.96 , $p < 0.05$). Hence,

the researcher rejected the null hypothesis and opted for the alternate hypothesis that there is a significant prediction of principal's social intelligence on teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The extent to which principal's problem solving skill predict teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State

The findings from result of analysis of research question one revealed that to a low extent principal's problem solving skill predicts teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. This means that to a low extent principals with strong problem-solving skills can address challenges efficiently, which enhances teacher morale, problem-solving principals manage resources efficiently, which improves productivity, principals who are skilled in problem-solving are often more adapt at mediating disputes, which keeps teachers focused on instruction, principals with strong problem-solving skills are able to make informed decisions that directly affect the teaching environment and problem-solving skills enable principals to facilitate collaboration among teachers. This finding is supported by Adebayo (2018) who examined the impact of leadership styles and problem-solving abilities of school principals on teachers' job satisfaction and productivity in selected secondary schools in Lagos State, Nigeria. The study concluded that principals with high problem-solving abilities were able to create a more conducive working environment, which led to increased teacher motivation, job satisfaction, and productivity. Teachers in schools where principals displayed effective problem-solving skills were more likely to engage actively in their teaching duties, collaborate with colleagues, and display better instructional practices. Okon (2021) conducted research on the role of school leadership in enhancing teacher productivity in Rivers State. The findings indicated a positive relationship between principals' problem-solving skills and teacher productivity. Principals who effectively managed resources, resolved conflicts, and provided clear guidance were more likely to have motivated and productive teachers. Teachers reported higher levels of job satisfaction and performance when they felt supported by problem-solving principals.

The extent to which principal's social intelligence predict teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State

The findings from result of analysis of research question two revealed that to a low extent principal's social intelligence predicts teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. This means that to a low extent principals with high social intelligence communicate clearly, which enhances understanding, socially intelligent principals can mediate disputes effectively, maintaining a positive work environment that prevents disruption, principals with strong social intelligence skills create a collegial school climate where teachers feel valued as well as productive, socially intelligent principals know how to inspire staff, recognise accomplishments, and encourage continuous improvement and

principals with high social intelligence set examples of cooperation, professionalism, which teachers often emulate. This finding is supported by Ajayi and Gberevbie (2021) who focused on the role of interpersonal relationships and social intelligence in teacher performance in Nigerian public secondary schools. It concluded that teachers who demonstrated strong interpersonal skills, a key component of social intelligence, were more likely to create an inclusive and supportive learning environment. This, in turn, led to increased student performance and improved overall teacher productivity. Eze (2022) research on teacher-student relationships and productivity in Rivers State's secondary schools showed that teachers who were skilled in interpersonal communication and empathetic towards their students' needs had higher levels of student engagement and academic achievement. The study also suggested that teachers' social intelligence contributed significantly to their ability to collaborate with colleagues, which further improved school productivity. Johnson et al. (2023) study in the *International Journal of Educational Psychology* found that social intelligence was a predictor of teacher job satisfaction and overall productivity. Teachers who scored higher in emotional and cognitive social intelligence were found to have better relationships with students and were able to create more engaging, effective learning environments. The study recommended that professional development programs for teachers include training on improving social intelligence to enhance their productivity.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that effective managerial competencies such as problem-solving skill and social intelligence play a pivotal role in enhancing teacher motivation, instructional delivery, and overall productivity. Empirical evidence suggests that schools led by principals who exhibit high levels of managerial competence tend to have more dedicated, innovative, and efficient teaching staff. These competencies not only create an enabling school environment but also foster professional growth and job satisfaction among teachers, which are essential for improving students' learning outcomes.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study as well as the conclusion, the researcher offers the following recommendations for implementation.

1. Government should organize regular training on analytical and critical thinking skills for principals to enhance effective resolution of academic and administrative issues.
2. It is important to establish performance appraisal frameworks that include feedback on principals' social interaction with staff and students, reinforcing the importance of relational leadership.

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